

Impact of Servant Leadership on Employee Performance in Public Sectors: The Mediating Role of Employee Job Satisfaction, Commitment, and the Moderating Role of Self-Esteem

Niu Xiongying & Zenebe Garedew Boku

Abstract:

The study explores the impact of servant leadership on employee performance in public sectors, the mediating role of employee job satisfaction, commitment, and the moderating role of self-esteem in the case of Ethiopia's public sector, Ministry of Revenue. The survey was adopted from the theory of servant leadership, employee job commitment, satisfaction, and performance. The study used primary and secondary data. And also used both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia has 200 public sectors and 158,617 employees. The researcher selected the Ministry of Revenue, which has 12 branches of taxpayers, and 3959 employees to address the study. Among those taxpayers, the investigator had chosen five branches. Data were collected from top-leaders, middle-leaders, and employees' of the organization. Questionnaires were distributed for 363 potential respondents whereas 345 were completed and retrieved successfully, which is about a 95.04% response rate. The data was described by testing of nonresponse bias, reliability and validity tests of measurement scales used in the study, descriptive analysis based on respondent's information, assessing data quality, the correlation between variables, and hypotheses testing using Structural Equation Model (SEM) and Regression Analysis. The data obtained from 38 structured survey questionnaires, and 5 unstructured interviews. To perform the data analysis, SPSS 26 and AMOS 24 statistical software versions were used. The study has a substantial role in bringing high employee job satisfaction, employee job commitment to purpose, and employee performance and enhances leadership competence in public sectors. Besides, the study provides knowledge into servant leadership literature and further research.

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1. Introduction

Leadership

Leadership is a part of the organization, and they are in charge of different missions such as planning, organizing, evaluating, and motivating (Hao & Yazdanifard, 2015). Leadership is a comprehensive behavioral and social science that influences its economic, political, and average structure success. It relies upon the high quality and well-organized preparation of the leader's insurance policies. The leader achieves the use of moral doable and seeks the greater truths of the followers in motion steps. The followers are extra pinnacle off (including the non-public envelopment of the follower and the follower's emotional and bodily restoration) due to interplay with the leader. The leader achieves this equal dominion for a man or woman as a chief seeks personal growth, renewal, regeneration, and prolonged stamina—mental, physical, and spiritual—through the leader-follower connections (Winston & Patterson, 2016). Individual personality with servant elements is considered in coping with these issues and challenges (Hashim, 2019). The current research has different purposes; it studies the relationship between servant leadership, employee commitment, job satisfaction, and employee performance. Besides, it examines the mediating role of employee commitment and job satisfaction and the moderating role of self-esteem between servant leadership and employee performance.

Servant Leadership Theories

Robert K. Greenleaf (1977) states that servant leadership is serving first and leading employees' mindset. The primary duty of managers is to prepare their followers. Besides, servant-leaders raise the value of the self-respect and wealth of the followers, serve others as first vital accountability, and struggle to meet the followers' physiological, psychological, and affective needs. Servant leadership shares some vague resemblances with democratic, transformational, and charismatic management styles, representing a follower-centric strategy (Greenleaf, 1977). According to Northouse (2016) and the website in Greenleaf's servant leadership's essential traits is listening, responsiveness, healing, consciousness, encouragement, forethought, stewardship, devotion to people's growth, and organizing Community. Servant leadership theoretically linked with a variety of extraordinary structural qualities; such as altruism, morality, spirituality, and authenticity; and focuses on the traditional resolved of the leaders first to serve, and self-concept of being a servant and steward, as well as the personal integrity of the leaders (Sendjaya & Sarros, 2015).

Employee Performance Theories

Performance is a multi-dimensional concept. Task performance refers to an individual's proficiency in performing activities, contributing to the organization's technical core. According to Rahardjo K. (2018), stellar performance influences employees' great and skills, i.e., things bearing to education, training, work ethic, work motivation, mental mindset, and the employees' bodily circumstances. Employee performance is essential as it displays employees' potential and capability in completing the duties allotted to them. Therefore, an organization desires to set clear and measurable criteria as a reference to measure employee performance (Triwahyuni & Ekowati, 2017). According to Kawiana, Dewi, Martini, and Suardana (2018), worker performance can also be defined as "the work high-quality and quantity finished by a worker in performing their obligations by the obligations given to them." Kirimi and Maende (2019) cited in a lookup paper on employee performance and development that employees are an organization's integral aspect.

Employee Commitment Theories

In the theories, Meyer and Allen have divided commitment into three categories: affective, normative, or continuance commitment (Meyer, Vandenberghe, and Becker, 2004). Hall (1970) noted that commitment is the degree to which organizational goals and individual goals are in the cycle. It demonstrates the magnitude to which workers recognize themselves with their organization and remain committed to its objectives. A mental state, commitment represents the ability of an individual to identify and involve in an organization.

Employee Satisfaction Theories

Employee job satisfaction has long been an issue for decades and is still one of the essential organizational concerns critical in improving workers' job satisfaction to enhance organizational performance (Hashim, Khattak & Kee, 2017). Employee satisfaction is an effective reaction to a job that results from the comparison of perceived outcomes with those desired. Employee satisfaction is a feeling of success and achievement that is connected directly to productivity and personal prosperity. (Al-Fakeh, Padlee, Omar, & Salleh, 2020). Job satisfaction is an individual's subjective viewpoint encompassing how an individual feels about his/her job and the employing organization. (Courtney & Younkyoung, 2017).

Self-Esteem Theories

Self-esteem has fascinated psychologists for over one hundred years and is one of the most widely studied social sciences concepts. Self-esteem is the negative or positive attitude that individuals have of themselves. The most frequently used measure of self-esteem broadly captures people's overall feelings of acceptance and respect. Self-esteem research generally has focused on global self-esteem, that is, one's feelings of self-worth. Self-worth is the degree to which individuals feel positive about themselves; that is, they feel excellent and valuable. Self-worth is rooted in the idea that individuals desire to see themselves favorably, and they act in a way that maintains and enhances this positive self-view (Bleidorn, Hufer, Kandler, Hopwood, & Riemann, 2018).

2. Relationship of Variables and Proposed Hypothesis

Servant Leadership and Employee Performance

The notion of prevalent leadership standard overall performance in conducting single determination via several kinds of collaborative things is character and administrator efforts (Lisbijanto & Budiyanto, 2014). The modern literature on servant leadership performs an unusual feature in aggregating workers' average overall performance (Olesia et al., 2013). Servant leadership contributed to increasing regulatory organization outcomes. Further, (Bass 2000) recommended that an effect of servant leadership on the organization due to its extraordinary worker efforts, and (Peterson et al., 2012 & Baykal et al., 2018) authors hooked up the large emphasis on servant leadership enhance the employee's outcome. Alagaraja and Shuck (2015) aimed to discover prevailing organizational arrangement viewpoints and worker commitment to recognize reasons related to improving person performance argue that employee performance can be increased through coaching and development. Furthermore, Thomas and Feldman (2010) adopted overall employee performance measures as core assignments, consisting of an in-role performance, protection performance, and creativity, observed through citizenship performance. Therefore, overall worker performance brings about innovation and firm performance as a whole, in such a way that worthwhile effort of fulfilled, inspired, and dedicated human assets produce revolutionary thoughts for new products or offerings and enlarge high-quality performance, operative performances, and client satisfaction immediately (Sadikoglu & Cemal, 2010).

Performance is the extent of the individual's real work performed to aid employees' way to useful resource precise necessities for a specific role (Shore and Tetrick, 1990; Sihombing et al., 2018). Performance is prejudiced with the resource of the excellent and competencies of workforces (education/training, work, ethic, work motivation, mental mindset and the physical kingdom of affairs of the employees, supporting facilities), work environment (occupational safety, occupational health, manufacturing facilities, technology), the welfare of personnel (wages/salaries, social security, professional security), and supra-facilities (Simanjuntak, 2001). Jaramillo et al. (2015) observed a significant and high-quality association between servant leadership and job performance. Performance can doubtlessly link to leadership when the leader's central focal point is to serve the followers (Joseph & Winston, 2005). As leaders conduct an impact on subordinate performance, a servant leader's subordinates have high degrees of engagement and loyalty, which can contribute toward greater degrees of performance (Hess, 2013). Therefore, based on the above theories, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 1: *Servant Leadership has a positive impact on employee performance.*

Servant leadership and employee commitment

A high-quality relationship between servant leadership and employee commitment has been conceptually proposed (Jacobs, 2006; Russell & Stone, 2002; Van Dierendonck, 2010). Commitment is usually a consequence of employees' superb perceptions concerning the organization (Jaramillo et al., 2015). A stress-free environment, appropriate family members with superiors, empowerment, and cognizance are the foremost predictors of employees' reliance and loyalty. Servant leadership behaviors make employees' commitment more excellent sturdy because behaviors like persuasive mapping, stewardship, and altruistic calling extend the stage of workers' enjoyment and commitment (Nehmeh, 2009; Liden et al., 2008). Luu (2016) also observed that servant leadership has a beautiful effect on employees' commitment, which can expand with the right conduct of leaders, such as employees' participation in decision-making processes, discussing with them their problems, continually wondering for their interest and growth, and empowering them to gain the targets. Therefore, based on the theories, the following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 2: *Servant leadership has a positive impact on employee job commitment.*

Servant Leadership and Employee Job Satisfaction

Employee job satisfaction has long been a difficulty for many years and is still one of the outstanding organizational issues essential in enhancing employees' job pride to improve organizational performance (Hashim, Khattak & Kee, 2017). Job pride fits between what the organization requires and what the employee is seeking and receiving. It is the internal feeling of a character related to fulfillment that may be qualitative or quantitative (Hashim, Khattak & Kee, 2017). It is affected through subculture and administration style, empowerment worker involvement, and self-sufficient work of groups. Job delight is a positive and pleasing emotional condition that one realizes from one's price (Wase, G. H., Suriani, L., & Mohd, B., 2020). Employee satisfaction is imperative to the improvement of any organization (Sarker & Ashrafi, 2018). According to Ali (2019), a standout amongst the most frequently viewed organizational sciences ideas is employee satisfaction. Employee pride is a full-size reaction to a job resulting from the contrast of perceived effects with those favoring (Sarker & Ashrafi, 2018).

Job satisfaction is lying on employees' pleasure and happiness, and it is the inner feeling of any person related to the job (Ilies & Judge, 2004; Rimes, 2012). Job satisfaction has two categories: interior pleasure, which is the inside need of the individual, and exterior satisfaction; however, based on financial rewards (Adeniji, 2011). Servant behaviors are

personnel oriented, care for people about their social problems, and inspire them to attain desire ambitions (Carter, 2011). Servant leadership is an excellent degree of positive attitudes, perceptions, and realistic expectations of the employees toward the organization where they work. Additionally, it directs the individual's positive emotions to the job (Sepahvand et al., 2015). Sepahvand et al. (2015) and Rozika et al. (2018) indicated that servant leadership significantly influences employee satisfaction. McNeff and Irving (2017) also confirmed that employee satisfaction was increased through servant leadership at the organization. A leader plays a dominant role in an organization. Those leaders who cultivate pleasant relationships by promoting career development will effectively enhance job satisfaction. Servant leaders must have a high degree of understanding of their employees, which enables the leaders to provide direction, which is the next key characteristic of servant leadership. All leaders provide direction, but servant leaders provide direction customized for each employee, which provides a higher level of accountability and leads to a higher quality relationship between employee and leader (Saleem et al., 2020). Therefore, leaders should always spend significant time and energy focused on understanding their style of leadership affects their employees. Based on these theories, the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: *Servant leadership has a positive impact on employee job satisfaction.*

The mediating role of Employee Job commitment

Servant leadership behaviors make employees' commitment more outstanding sturdy (Liden et al., 2008). Luu (2016) also observed that servant leadership has a beautiful effect on employees' commitment. Madhuri et al. (2014) noted that organizational commitment has a more significant effect on an employee's job performance (Mathew, 2018). Commitment can expand with leaders' right conduct, such as employees' participation in decision-making processes, discussing their problems, continually wondering for their interest and growth, and empowering them to gain the targets (Kim, S. J., Song, M., Hwang, E., Roh, T., & Song, J. H., 2020), and this may increase the performance of employees. Consequently, the theories imply that employee job commitment has a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance. The following hypothesis is proposed:

Hypothesis 4: *Employee Job Commitment plays a mediating role between Servant Leadership and Employee Performance.*

The Mediating role Employee Job Satisfaction

A servant leader is a mindset to perform a crucial role in an organization's work surroundings and personnel (Rimes, 2011; Azizullah & Hashim, 2019). Ding et al. (2012) have proved that there is a vital relationship between servant leader's attitudes and job satisfaction, which enhances worker performance. Effective planning and stewardship are servant leadership features, growing work satisfaction, and dedication (Carter, 2012). Adeniji (2011) also mentions that pride, such as an excellent working environment, advertising chances, recognition, and proper relation, builds employees' faith and amplifies employee performance. Employee job performance has continually been a significant task in organizational leadership. Adopting positive ways to encourage employees to achieve and supply more excellent job performance and enlarge corporate competitiveness is the primary objective of every organization that recommended that employee performance deteriorate. Therefore, it believes that worker performance increases organization success. The personnel is regarded as the predominant organization resource that facilitates everyday operations (Mudah, Rafiki & Harahap 2014).

Similarly, Oluwafemi (2010) asserted that organizational effectiveness and efficiency rely on cheerful and efficient personnel. Chiniara and Bentein (2016) discovered that servant

leadership indirectly influences job performance; servant leaders provide autonomy and self-sufficiency, which affects the more significant stages of understanding of their subordinates. Other studies have identified an excellent effect of servant leadership on employee performance (Schaubroeck et al., 2011), association performance (Peterson et al., 2012), the economic performance of the organization (Ruschman, 2002), and individual overall performance (Jaramillo et al., 2015). Collaborate leadership with the more excellent overall performance at the organizational level, the leader as a personnel supervisor would also directly influence the person. Servant leadership plays a vital role in an organization's work environment and employee satisfaction (Rimes, 2011), and commitment largely depends on employees' job satisfaction (McCann et al., 2014). Therefore, the theories it proposed that:

Hypothesis 5: *Job Satisfaction plays a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance.*

Employee Performance and Self-Esteem

Self-esteem is the negative or positive attitude that individuals have of themselves. Self-esteem is linked to concepts like self-confidence, self-respect, and self-worth. The most frequently used measure of self-esteem largely captures people's overall feelings of acceptance and respect. Self-esteem research generally has focused on global self-esteem, that is, one's feelings of self-worth. Self-worth is the degree to which individuals feel positive about themselves, that is, they feel that they are good and valuable. It is self-acceptance or self-respect (Rosenberg et al. 1995). Self-worth is rooted in the idea that individuals desire to see themselves favorably, and they act in a way that maintains and enhances this positive self-view. This desire has been referred to as the self-esteem motive or the self-enhancement motive (Leary 2007). Employees' experience in and self-esteem, particularly as a superior-subordinate relationship is characterized by a certain organization strongly influences their self-esteem, which is evident in their attitudes and behavior. The interactions they have with their manager will contribute significantly to their organizational experience amount of tension. Therefore, from the theories, we proposed that:

Hypothesis 6: *Self-esteem will have positive relations between servant leadership and employee performance.*

Conceptual Research Model

The conceptual model of the contemporary study as illustrated in Diagram 1 explains the following proposed hypothesis. It supposed that the practices of servant leadership to directly linked to employee commitment, employee satisfaction, and employee job satisfaction. Additionally; it suggests that employee commitment and employee job satisfaction mediates the impact of servant leadership and employee performance. Moreover, self-esteem moderates the relationship between servant leadership and employee performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Research Model

3. Methodology

Research is undertaken within a framework of a set of philosophies (approaches) and also it uses procedures, methods, and techniques that have been tested for their validity and reliability. The primary research paradigm as the basic set of beliefs that guides this study is positivism. This view argues that both scientific reasoning and common sense reasoning is essentially the same thing.

Ethiopia is located in the horn of Africa and it's a landlocked country bordered on the north and northeast by Eritrea, on the east by Djibouti and Somalia, on the south by Kenya, on the northwest by Sudan and on the southwest by South Sudan. Ethiopia has a high central plateau that varies from 1,290 to 3,000 m (4,232 to 9,843 ft.) above sea level, with the highest mountain reaching 4,533 m (14,872 ft.).

The research design embodies an explanatory approach as its purpose, which is used to examine the relationship between servant leadership and employee job performance as well investigate the mediating role of job satisfaction and job commitment between servant leadership and employee performance, and the moderating role of self-esteem between servant leadership and employee performance. This study's strategies are case study and primary data is used regarding data type, and interview and questionnaire for data collection technique applied to cross-sectional data. A cross-sectional survey was used in collecting data from respondents. This study's strategy is a case study that helps to explore the attitude and experience of leadership regarding commitment, satisfaction, self-esteem, and performance of employee, middle level, and top-level leaders within the scope of analysis.

Source and Method of Data Collection

Methods of Data Collection: For the assessment and evaluation of the servant leadership and employee performance in the Ministry of Revenue, primary data is collected and used for analysis. Primarily is collected through questionnaires and interviews. In this study, mainly close-ended questionnaires are used primarily as tools for gathering relevant data. Furthermore, some open-ended questionnaires are also used to solicit in-depth and relevant information. The study used both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The data was analyzed by SPSS 26 and AMOS 24 statistical software versions. Moreover, the data obtained from 38 structured survey questionnaires, and 5 unstructured interviews.

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity is the degree to which a test measures what it purports to measure (Creswell, 2009). Validity is defined as the accuracy and meaningfulness of the inferences, which are based on the research results. Results obtained from the analysis of the data represent the phenomena under study to the degree. For the data to be reliable the first criteria is Cronbach's Alpha test. According to Taherdoost (2016) and Whitley (2013), Cronbach's Alpha should be greater than or equal to 0.70 for data reliability. Secondly, corrected item-total correlations should be greater than or equal to 0.35 to be retained. The third one is inter-item correlation and this value should not exceed 0.8 for all pairs. The following table shows the reliability test based on Cronbach's alpha test

Table 1. Reliability Statistics

Contracts	Cronbach's Alpha Before	No. of Items Future	No. of items dropped	No. items retained	Cronbach's Alpha After
Employee Servant Leadership	0.894	7		7	0.894
Employee Job Commitment	0.815	10	1	9	0.864
Employee Job Satisfaction	0.763	9	2	7	0.822
Employee Job Performance	0.739	7	1	6	0.81
Employee Self-Esteem	0.841	5		5	0.841

Source: Researcher AMOS output

Table-1 presents the result of Cronbach's Alpha before and after variable extraction. Based on the variable extraction method some variables deleted due to item correlation and others were retained. For retained variables, Cronbach's Alpha is again computed and the result is displayed in the last column of the table. The result shows that Cronbach's Alpha for each variable is greater than 0.7, which means that data is reliable for further analysis.

AS Suggested by Zwick and Velicer (1982), reliability between (0.70 to 0.90) is said to be highly reliable. Thus, each variable in this study fits the purpose. Although reliability is important for the study, it is not sufficient unless combined with validity. In other words, for a test to be reliable, it also needs to be valid (Zwick and Velicer, 1982) Moreover, Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has been developed to compute the validity of the measurement scale. The developed full confirmatory Factor Analysis Measurement Model using AMOS software in the first place was found to be inadmissible. After the variable was deleted and further trial convergent, discriminant validity holds, and the CFA found to be a good fit model (detail discussion given in chapter 4).

Description of Variables of Interest

The conceptual framework of the study is verifying the impact of servant leadership measured by quality, skills, knowledge, and interpersonal communications on employee performance. The conceptual model, variables, and hypothesis are adopting and modifying from descriptive and empirical research studies. The variable of interest of this study is the effect of servant leadership on employee performance and which is measured as employee satisfaction gained and commitment discharged per employee during the period. Variables of interest used in modeling can be divided into four types: The "dependent variables" "independent variable", mediating variables", "moderating variable". Data for each variable is based on Likert scale qualitative information soliciting way of unit measurement

Variable Descriptions

Dependent Variable: The dependent variable represents the output or effect, or is tested to see if it is the effect. The dependent variable of the model is employee performance (capacity, confidence, dedication).

Independent Variable: The independent variables represent the inputs or causes, or are tested to see if they are the cause. Other variables may also be observed for various reasons. The Independent variable of the model is servant leadership measured by quality, skills, knowledge, and interpersonal communications

Mediating Variable: Job Satisfaction (internal working condition) is a mediating variable that plays a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance. Moreover, Job Commitment (decision-making, team spirit, and quality service) plays a mediating role between Servant Leadership (quality, skills, knowledge, and interpersonal communications) and Employee performance

Moderating: The moderation variable is self-esteem. Self-esteem (respecting and acceptance) is a moderating variable that plays a moderating role between servant leadership (quality, skills, knowledge, and interpersonal communications) and employee performance.

Econometric Model Specification: Single and multiple regression models (path analysis) used in a series of forms to investigate the mediating effect of job commitment on the relationships between servant leadership and performance. For this purpose, the study established three regression models as under.

Model 1: $Y = \gamma_0 + \gamma X + \varepsilon_1$ Equation (1)

Model 2: $Y = \gamma'_0 + \gamma' X + \beta M + \varepsilon_2$ Equation (2)

Model 3: $M = \alpha_0 + \alpha X + \varepsilon_3$ Equation (3)

Where:

Y is the outcome variable = Job performance,

X is independent variable = Servant leadership,

M is the mediator = Job satisfaction and job commitment

γ is total effect =that demonstrates the zero-order correlation between X and Y (ignoring M) in the first equation,

γ' is direct effect = that demonstrates the Beta coefficient relating the independent (X) to the outcome (Y) adjusted for the effects of the mediator(s)(M), in the second equation,

β = is the Beta coefficient relating the mediator(s) (M) to the outcome (Y) adjusted for the effects of independent (X), in the second equation,

α = is the Beta coefficient that demonstrates the zero-order correlation between X and M (ignoring Y), in the third equation.

ε_1 , and ε_3 code unexplained variability of equations (1), (2), and (3) respectively, and γ_0 , γ'_0 , and α_0 are the intercepts of equations (1), (2), and (3) respectively (Lukas, 2015).

Ethical Consideration

In this study confidentiality and anonymity have been given due attention. The purpose and significance of study were communicated with the respondents and assured them that the information solicited is only used for academic purpose and all the information obtained are kept confidential. Moreover, they were assured that their organizational affiliation and names are kept anonymous. After, they have been guaranteed this ethical consideration they voluntarily took part in the study

4. Data Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation

This section presents data analysis and discusses the results. It describes testing of nonresponse bias, reliability and validity tests of measurement scales used in the study, descriptive analysis based on respondent's information, assessing data quality, the correlation between variables, and hypotheses testing using Structural Equation Model (SEM) and regression analysis. Moreover, a summary of hypothesis testing is presented. To perform the data analysis, SPSS 26 and AMOS 24 statistical software were used

Respondents Demographic Profile: Data were collected from top-level leaders, middle-level leaders, and employees of the Ministry of Revenue. Questionnaires were distributed for 363 potential respondents whereas 345 were completed and retrieved successfully, which is about a 95.04% response rate.

Testing Non-response Bias: Before testing for validity and reliability test of a variable in a relationship, checking the non-response bias of the variables used in the model to be estimated is much important in data analysis. In this study dropped item due to the total item correlation are one (EJC6) from the employee job commitment dimension, two (EJS8 and EJS9) from the employee job satisfaction dimension, and one (EJP1) from employee job performance (see annex 1).

Reliability and Validity Test

Reliability Test: For the data to be reliable the first criteria are Cronbach's Alpha test. According to Taherdoost (2016) and Whitley (2013), Cronbach's Alpha should be greater than or equal to 0.70 for data reliability. Secondly, corrected item-total correlations should be greater than or equal to 0.35 to be retained. The third one is inter-item correlation and this value should not exceed 0.8 for all pairs. The following table shows the reliability test based on Cronbach's alpha test.

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The above table presents the result of Cronbach's Alpha before and after variable extraction. Based on the variable extraction method some variables were deleted due to item correlation and others were retained. For retained variables, Cronbach's Alpha is again computed and the result is displayed in the last column of the table. The result shows that Cronbach's Alpha for each variable is greater than 0.7, which means that data is reliable for further analysis.

AS Suggested by Zwick and Velicer (1982), reliability between (0.70 to 0.90) is said to be highly reliable. Thus, each variable in this study fits the purpose. Although reliability is important for the study, it is not sufficient unless combined with validity. In other words, for a test to be reliable, it also needs to be valid (Zwick and Velicer, 1982)

The validity of the Data: Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) has been developed to compute the validity of the measurement scale. The developed full confirmatory Factor Analysis Measurement Model using AMOS software in the first place was found to be inadmissible. After variable deleted and further trial convergent and discriminant validity holds and the CFA found to be a good fit model (detail discussion given in 5.1)

Assessing the Quality of Data:

Assessing sample size: For Structural Equation Modeling the sample size should be at least 100 to 200. The sample size for this study is 363, which is large enough to fit to undertake SEM for analysis.

Assessing Common Method Bias (CMB): According to Podsakoff, Mackenzie, and Podsakoff (2003), the first factor of un-rotated factor analysis should be less than 50% to be free from CMB. In this study, the first factor accounted for 15.933 % (See annex 2). The results suggested that there was no common variable. Enders (2004) stated that, Assessing Missing Data is a missing rate of 15% to 20% was common in educational and psychological studies. In this study due to unanswered and unengaged responses (less than 0.05 percent), the researcher reduced the respondents from 363 to 345 usable questionnaires. Assessing outliers is absolute values of frequency distributions of Z-scores are used to find uni-variate outliers. If the absolute value of the Z-score is greater than 3.29 with $p < .001$, it indicates that there is a uni-variate outlier. In this study, no outliers were observed. Assessing Linearity Assumption means the predictor variables in the regression have a straight-line relationship with the outcome variable or Observations are independent of each other. In this study, Observations are independent of each other showing that data is linear.

Assessing Multicollinearity Assumption: The correlation between the response and predictors has expected nonetheless correlation among predictors is displeasing. In regression, analysis multicollinearity can be measured using the variance inflation factor (VIF) and the value of tolerance. The VIF assesses how much the variance of an estimated regression coefficient increases if multicollinearity exists. If no factors are correlated, the VIFs will all be less than 10 (rule of thumb).

Table 3. Collinearity Diagnosis

		Collinearity Statistics	
No.	Independent Variable	Tolerance	VIF
1	ESL	.856	1.168
2	ESE	.856	1.168

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Job Performance

Source: Researcher AMOS output

The value of VIF is very close to one, which shows that the predictor and predicted variables are not correlated. Thus, multicollinearity is not a problem in this study. Therefore, allowed to proceed to further analysis. Moreover, the Tolerance level, which shows the variability of the independent variable that is not explained by the other independent variables, is 0.856 which is greater than that of 0.1 indicating no collinearity. Assessing Normality Assumption used a common rule of thumb test for normality is to run descriptive statistics to get skewness and kurtosis and use the criterion that skewness and kurtosis should be within the -2 to +2 for data to be normally distributed. The result shows that for each variable skewness and kurtosis are within the range of -2 to +2 (see Annex 3). Thus, data is normally distributed around mean and standard deviation.

Factor analysis: Factor analysis is used to remove redundancy from a set of correlated variables. In this study, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) are used to remove redundancy.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA): EFA is a variable reduction technique, which identifies the number of latent constructs and the underlying factor structure of a set of variables. The

researcher uses SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 26 to perform EFA and reliability analysis.

Factor Extraction: Based on the assumptions of EFA, the researcher used the principal component method for the factor extraction with the results of the uni-variate analysis and used Variamax rotation to carry out factor interpretation. The factorability of any data is evaluated by statistical measures generated by SPSS: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of Sphericity. This study also used Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin (KMO) for a measure of sampling adequacy, which varies from 0.5 to 1, and Bartlett's test of Sphericity. This study's Sphericity test set the null hypothesis that the population correlation matrix is an identity matrix whereas the alternative hypothesis says that it is not. If Bartlett's test of Sphericity's significance value is less than 0.05 that is the data, DO NOT produce an identity matrix.

Table 4. Sample Adequacy Statistics

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.840
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	5277.817
	Df	561
	Sig.	0.000

Source: International Encyclopedia of Statistical Science (Lovric, M.,2011)

The result shows that the sampling adequacy suggested by KMO is 0.84, which is marvelous the sphericity test result also shows that the data population correlation matrix is different from being identity since the the significance value is 0.000.

Communality measures the percentage of variables variation that is explained by the factors. While performing EFA using Principal Axis Factoring with Promax rotation, Osborne, Costello, & Kellow (2008) suggests the communalities above 0.4 are acceptable. However, Child. D (2006) suggests that the value of communality below 0.2 should be removed since it is the manifestation of omitted variable, leading to bias in the analysis. Omitted variable bias leads to incorrect regression coefficient estimation and variance as well as wrong acceptance and rejection of the hypothesis. In this study, the extraction column of all variables is greater than 0.4. whereas, only ESL4, EJC2, and EJC4 extraction column values between 0.2 and 0.4 (of course, struggle to load significantly on any factor). Therefore, ESL4, EJC2, and EJC4 are candidates for removal after the pattern matrix is observed. *Total Variance Explained* is used to assess the variance in all variables, which are accounted for by a single factor. In this study, the extraction is obtained at the first trial; therefore, the total variance explained doesn't change. Factor rotation is used to check and improve the interpretability of factors. Rotation is used to maximize the loadings of each variable on one of the extracted factors at the same time it minimizes the loading on all other factors. Rotation matrices are square matrices, with real entries. More specifically, they can be characterized as orthogonal matrices with determinant 1; that is, a square matrix R is a rotation matrix if and only if $R^T = R^{-1}$ and $\det R = 1$. In this study, the rotated component matrix is orthogonal, which highly improves the interpretability of the factors under consideration.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis: CFA is used whether or not a defined factor model fits an observed set of data. Structural equation modeling (SEM) is a multivariate statistical framework that is used to model complex relationships between directly and indirectly (latent) observed variables. In this study, the measurement model and structural model of structural equation modeling are used.

Measurement Model: The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) measurement model is the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and depicts the pattern of observed variables for those latent constructs in the hypothesized model. The examination process of the instrument for convergent validity is done by convergent and discriminate validity.

Convergent Validity: Standardized regression weights should be above 0.5, with values of above 0.7 optimal. SMC can also be used to assess item reliability. An SMC between 0.3 and 0.5 indicates that the item is a weak but adequate measure of the construct. An SMC of 0.5 calculates to a standardized loading of 0.7, which indicates that the item reflects the construct very well. In this study, different measures are used that are helpful to measure construct validity. The first one is standardized regression loadings (SRL) (which demands a value greater than 0.5) to be valid, the second one is significant p-value (at 95% confidence interval) with a critical ratio (Z-values outside -1.96 to +1.96) and finally, squared multiple correlations (SMC which needs to be greater than 0.4) are considered to hold convergent validity.

Discriminant Validity: Discriminant validity is a measure of the extent to which one latent variable differentiates from other latent variables. The correlation between different constructs is used to measure discriminant validity. High correlations (above 0.8 or 0.9) between constructs indicate a lack of discriminant validity.

Goodness of Fit: The Goodness of Fit (GoF) of a statistical hypothesis tests to look through how well the data fits into the set of observations. In this study, GOF indicators (absolute measures, incremental measures, and parsimonious) are used to fit measures.

Table 5. Final CFA Measurement Model

After Final Variable Deleted							
Chi-Square		Absolut Fit Indices		Incremental Fit Indices		Parsimony Fit Indices	
X2	150.313	RMSEA	0.039	CFI	0.979	PCFI	0.799
Df	98	RMR	0.035	IFI	0.979	PNFI	0.769
X2/Df	1.534	CMIN/DF	1.534	TLI	0.974	GFI	0.949
Factor Loadings ***=p<0.001, **=p<0.01, *=p<0.05 Rows with blank space indicate indicator is set as default							
Item <--- Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	SMC	Comments	
ESL1 <--- ESL	0.756				0.572	Convergent Validity Holds	
ESL2 <--- ESL	0.823	0.073	15.503	***	0.677	Convergent Validity Holds	
ESL3 <--- ESL	0.801	0.073	15.062	***	0.642	Convergent Validity Holds	
ESL4 <--- ESL	0.788	0.075	14.785	***	0.621	Convergent Validity Holds	
ESL5 <--- ESL	0.777	0.075	14.558	***	0.604	Convergent Validity Holds	
ESL7 <--- ESL	0.691	0.082	12.794	***	0.478	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJS1 <--- EJS	0.699				0.488	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJS2 <--- EJS	0.813	0.099	12.182	***	0.66	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJS3 <--- EJS	0.719	0.105	11.342	***	0.517	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJS4 <--- EJS	0.69	0.105	10.969	***	0.476	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJP2 <--- EJP	0.69				0.476	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJP3 <--- EJP	0.797	0.089	12.415	***	0.634	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJP4 <--- EJP	0.864	0.098	12.435	***	0.747	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJC5 <--- EJC	0.797				0.626	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJC7 <--- EJC	0.877	0.069	15.394	***	0.675	Convergent Validity Holds	
EJC8 <--- EJC	0.767	0.063	14.466	***	0.681	Convergent Validity Holds	

Source: Researcher AMOS output

From the table above all the model fits and all the required validity ranges are within the ranges, therefore, the measurement model can be converted to a structural model.

Figure 2. Structural Model

Table 6. The size, direction, and significance of the estimated structural parameters

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Remark
EJS <--- ESL	0.694	0.319	2.177	0.029	Significant
EJC <--- ESL	-0.04	0.064	-0.624	0.533	Not Significant
EJP <--- ESL	-0.731	0.291	-2.515	0.012	Significant
EJP <--- EJS	0.031	0.08	0.391	0.696	Not Significant
EJP <--- EJC	0.261	0.062	4.226	0	Significant

Source: Researcher AMOS output

In the above table, there are five criteria for mediation and non-mediation. Three patterns consistent with mediation and two with non-mediation: 1) Complementary mediation: Mediated or indirect effect (a x b) and direct effect (c) both exist (significant) and point in the same direction. (Partial Mediation) 2) Competitive mediation: Mediated or indirect effect (a x b) and direct effect (c) both exist (significant) and point in opposite directions. (Partial Mediation) 3) Indirect-only mediation: Mediated or indirect effect (a x b) exists, but no direct effect. (Full Mediation) 4) Direct-only non-mediation: Direct effect (c) exists (significant), but no indirect effect. 5) No-effect non-mediation: Neither direct effect nor indirect effect exists. It occurs when both direct and indirect effects are insignificant.

Table 7. Direct and Indirect Effect and Mediating Variables Results

Hypothesis	Exogenous Variables	Mediator Variable	Endogenous Variable	Path Coefficients	P-value	Results	Type of the mediating Effect
DIRECT EFFECT							
H1	ESL		EJP	-0.731(a)	0.012	Supported	
H2	ESL		EJC	-0.042	0.533	Not Supported	
H3	ESL		EJS	0.694	0.029	Supported	
INDIRECT EFFECT							
H4	ESL	EJC	EJP	-0.186 (a*b1)	0.003(**)	Supported	Complementary mediation
H5	ESL	EJS	EJP	(0.023)(a*b2)	0.013(*)	Supported	Complementary mediation

From the result, both variables Commitment and Satisfaction mediate the relationship between Servant Leadership and Job Performance, and the mediation for both is Complementary Mediation.

The moderation effect of Employee Self Esteem

Table 8. Moderating Variable Result

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
EJP <--- ESL	-0.234	0.047	-4.983	***
EJP <--- ESL_ESE	0.056	0.013	4.396	***
EJP <--- ESE	0.084	0.04	2.075	0.038

Source: Researcher AMOS output

From the criteria and the results, Self-esteem moderates the relationship between Servant Leadership and Job Performance.

Figure 3. Moderation Effect

5. Findings of Empirical Results and Discussion

In line with the objectives, six research hypotheses were formulated in chapter one. In this section, these research hypotheses were tested as follows:

Table 9. Direct and indirect effects of exogenous and mediating variables

Hypothesis	Exogenous Variables	Mediator Variable	Endogenous Variable	Path Coefficients	P-value	Results	Type of the mediating Effect
DIRECT EFFECT							
H1	ESL		EJP	-0.731(a)	0.012	Supported	
H2	ESL		EJC	-0.042	0.533	Not Supported	
H3	ESL		EJS	0.694	0.029	Supported	
INDIRECT EFFECT							
H4	ESL	EJC	EJP	-0.186 (a*b1)	0.003(**)	Supported	Complementary mediation
H5	ESL	EJS	EJP	(0.023)(a*b2)	0.013(*)	Supported	Complementary mediation

Source: Researcher AMOS output

Hypothesis Test Result of the Study

Hypothesis 1: Servant leadership has a positive impact on job performance.

Based on the summary of the statistical estimate (table above), the impact of servant leadership on job performance is (p = 0.012). Therefore, servant leadership affects employee performance positively.

Hypothesis 2: Servant leadership does not affect employee commitment positively.

Based on the summary of the statistical estimate (table above), the impact of servant leadership on commitment (p = 0.533) indicates that there is no evidence to affect the hypothesis positively. Consequently, servant leadership does not affect employee commitment positively.

Hypothesis 3: Servant leadership and employee job satisfaction have a positively relationship.

Based on the summary of the statistical estimate (table above), the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction (p = 0.029) indicates that servant leadership affects employee job satisfaction positively.

Hypothesis 4: Employee commitment plays a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance.

As indicated in the path analysis result, the result shows a significant indirect effect of job commitment ($\beta = -0.186$, $p=0.003$). Hence, commitment mediates the relationship between Servant Leadership and job Performance, and the mediation played by job commitment is complementary mediation.

Hypothesis 5: Job satisfaction plays a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance.

Likewise, the path analysis result shows a significant indirect effect of job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.023$, $p=0.013$). Hence, job Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Servant Leadership and job Performance, and mediation played by job satisfaction is complementary mediation.

Hypothesis 6: Self-esteem plays a mediating role between servant leadership and employee performance.

Empirical Results and Discussion

The overall objectives of this study were to investigate the impact of servant leadership (quality, skills, knowledge, and interpersonal communications) on Employee Performance in the Ethiopian Ministry of Revenue with mediating role job satisfaction and commitment as well as moderating of self-esteem. Structural equation model with regression analysis used to test the existence of mediation effect of job satisfaction and commitment and the moderating role of self-esteem. The major findings and discussion of the data analysis are as follows. A majority of the respondents are ordinary employees (non-managerial groups) which are about 77.7 percent followed by the middle leader (18.0 percent) and Top leader (4.3 percent). Those who have long service above 5 years in the ministry office 78.2 percent, which is very much helpful to solicit enough information about servant leadership, employees commitment, and satisfaction.

The contribution of servant leadership for employee commitment and satisfaction is found to be greater so the organization should continue to improve in servant leadership. According to the descriptive statistics, it is found that among four components (ESL, EJC, EJP, and ESE). Cronbach's Alpha for servant leadership is high (0.894), implying that servant leadership is highly oriented to the organization's laws and regulations. Other most components are also showing slight differences as they progress from the start to achieving the organization's vision. The correlation coefficient between servant leadership and commitment, satisfaction and performance, separately ranges from -0.007 to 0.045 (see annex). Indicating that there is a significant as well as positive or correlation among the variables of interest. The result shows that job commitment was the most correlated variable with job performance. The path analysis result shows that servant leadership on employee job performance shown that servant leadership explains 73% of the variation in employee performance that significantly affects job performance.

Servant leadership culture in the organization becomes a leading edge of employee commitment, satisfaction, and quality service delivery. Hence, it provides a dynamic and flexible working environment where employees are motivated and have greater self-esteem for their careers. Therefore, the more the organization focuses on servant leadership delivery, the more employees are satisfied and committed to the organization. The result is consistent with empirical studies, which supported the positive association between servant leadership and employee commitment as well as satisfaction. The study's findings also show a significant relationship between independent variables themselves (satisfaction, commitment, and performance). The path analysis result shows the effect of job performance on job commitment shown, 26.1 % of the variation in employee's job performance with a positive significant coefficient. It shows that employee commitment, which is expected to be sustainable, can highly predict employee's performance in the organization, which could help as input for servant leadership.

The study's result suggested a positive and significant relation between servant leadership and employee job performance and servant leadership and employee job satisfaction. However, the result shows that the positive relationship between servant leadership and employee job commitment is not supported. Servant leadership and employee job performance. Servant leadership's contribution to employees' performance is high so the ministry office should continue to improve and update servant leadership theories to ensure continued committed leadership and achieve the national objective. As servant leadership prevalent in the ministry office, more likely committed and high performing employee is looking for the sector, which further enhances the organization's quality of service delivery with the lowest investment. Further, employee job commitment mediates the relationship between servant leadership and job performance. Besides, employee job satisfaction also mediates the relationship between Servant Leadership and Job Performance. Mediation for both is complementary mediation.

The moderation variable result shows that self-esteem moderates the relationship between servant Leadership and job Performance. Generally, the result of the analysis shows that different servant leadership with different employees (different in performance, commitment, self-esteem) in or has different results on employee's satisfaction, commitment, and self-esteem. This implied for leaders that they have to understand the appropriate servant leadership theory and used it for the best of their organization while holding employee's commitment and satisfaction and performance in account to offer quality service for the general public.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

This study aims to critically analyze the impact of servant leadership on employee performance with the mediating role of satisfaction and commitment between servant leadership and performance as well as the moderating role of self-esteem between servant leadership and performance in the Ethiopian Ministry of Revenue. As per the objective and finding of the study the under stated conclusion worth drawn. The result of the study could enable us to conclude that servant leadership has a positive impact on employee job performance in the Ethiopian Ministry of Revenue. The researcher distributed a sample of 363 to employees where 345 questioners were fully responded. The questioner used were assessed its reliability in the context of the relationship between servant leadership and performance. Cronbach's alpha was used by which all the variables are consistent and reliable. Data quality analysis was under taken so as to filter the fitted data for analysis. All the test result shows data is allowed to use for further analysis.

Path analysis estimation indicated that there is a positive relationship between servant leadership and performance as well as servant leadership and satisfaction. However, there the relationship between servant leadership and job commitment is not positive in the study. The study's findings concluded job satisfaction, job commitment mediates the relationship between servant leadership, and performance and the mediation for both were complementary mediation in the Ministry of Revenue. Thus, The hypothesis that stated the impact of servant leadership on employee performance, the mediating role of job satisfaction on the relationship between servant leadership and performance, and the moderating role of self-esteem role in moderating the relationship between servant leadership and performance is supported. Whereas the the positive relationship between servant leadership and performance is not supported. The impact of servant leadership on commitment ($p = 0.533$) indicating that there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis and the conclusion is in favor

of the alternative hypothesis. Therefore, servant leadership does not affect employee commitment positively.

Moreover, the study supported that there is no statistically significant difference among employees assigned at different levels (top leader, middle leader, and none-leader) in perceiving the impact of servant leadership on employee performance, which are, vary in gender in the Ministry office. There is a statistically significant difference among employees at a different level in perceiving the relationship between servant leadership and employee performance based on the Ministry office's age category and experiences.

Another important conclusion is that employees with different experiences have different understandings concerning servant leadership's impact on employee performances, indicating that employees with a different year of service had different ways of understanding the mediating role and moderating role on the relationship between servant leadership and performance. There is a significant relationship between independent variables themselves (satisfaction, commitment, and performance). The path analysis result shows the effect of job performance on job commitment shown, 26.1 % of the variation in employee's job performance with a positive significant coefficient. It shows that employee commitment, which is expected to be sustainable, can highly predict employee's performance in the organization, which could help as input for servant leadership.

Recommendation

Servant leadership's contribution to employees' " performance" is high so the ministry office should continue to make improve and updates servant leadership theories to ensure continues committed leadership and achieve the national objective. Since employee commitment and servant, leadership shows no positive relationship, and the organization has to focus on focuses delivery of servant leadership that encourages employee commitment to achieve the Ministry of Revenue's goals. Employees with higher experience well understood the impact of servant leadership on job performance so that the regulatory bodies of the Ministry of Revenue have to give due emphasis to satisfy and retain such employees.

The impact of servant leadership on all variables under consideration was not positive. Therefore, the Ministry of revenue shall give due emphasis to employee job commitment and development. Improving employee job commitment would improve the overall Ministry office servant leadership relationship with employee performance. In general, the organization had better continue focusing on the areas in which it is doing well (satisfaction and performance) and find ways to improve those areas it is doing not good (commitment and servant leadership).

6. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Although this study provided significant contributions to the existing literature, it has several limitations that need to be addressed in the future. Firstly, the data collections were performed from the Ministry of Revenue of the federal democratic republic of Ethiopia only. Therefore, the future researcher could collect and use a variety of data from other Ministries and the Regional State government of the public sectors. Besides, in the study, cross-sectional data have been collected that can create the possibility of common method biases by limiting the ability to achieve a causal inference. Thus, to further alleviate this issue and make a stronger conclusion, it is suggested that longitudinal data and vast studies should be conducted in the future, as it will observe the subject matter more in detail over a specific period.

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